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***Corresponding**

Author:

Ogboeli G. P.

*Institute of Geo-Science
and Environmental
Management, Rivers State
University, Nkpolu
Oroworukwo, Port
Harcourt*

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Temporal Variations in Road Traffic Crash Severity in Rivers State: from Minor to Fatal Cases (2015–2024)

Ogboeli G. P.^{1}, Nimame, P. K.², Eni S.³,
Amos-Bein E. B.⁴*

*^{1,2,3,4}Institute of Geo-Science and Environmental
Management, Rivers State University, Nkpolu
Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt*

ABSTRACT

Road traffic crashes (RTCs) remain a major public health and economic concern in Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, where oil and gas operations, dense commercial transport, and infrastructural gaps heighten risk. This study examined temporal patterns in RTC incidence and severity in Rivers State (mainly Port Harcourt) from 2015–2024, using data from the Federal Road Safety Corps and the National Bureau of Statistics. A total of 963 crashes involving 1,571 vehicles and 2,322 persons were analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and linear and segmented regression ($p < 0.05$). Serious injuries were the most frequent outcome (47.25%, $n=455$), followed by minor injuries (30.32%, $n=292$) and fatalities (20.35%, $n=196$), indicating a substantial burden of severe non-fatal harm. Passenger cars (32.85%) were most involved, alongside minibuses (21.77%) and trucks (17.95%). Commercial vehicles (51.88%) slightly exceeded private ownership (46.09%). Mean annual counts were 96.3 crashes, 159.9 injuries, and 4.7 fatalities. Significant temporal variations were observed in crash severity, vehicle type, and ownership ($p < 0.01$). Overall crashes ($-5.56/\text{year}$), injuries ($-6.82/\text{year}$), and fatalities ($-0.43/\text{year}$) declined, peaking in 2018–2019 (~134–138 cases) before a sharp drop in 2020 linked to COVID-19 restrictions, reaching 47 cases in 2024. Despite fewer crashes, the severity of post-2020 crashes worsened: fatal proportions rose by 1.87% per year ($p = 0.005$), serious injuries increased marginally, and minor injuries declined by 3.06% per year ($p = 0.002$). Segmented regression confirmed a significant post-2020 rise in fatality rates ($p=0.028$), with case fatality averaging 4.88% and exceeding 7% in several post-pandemic years. The findings highlight a paradox of declining incidence but rising lethality, likely reflecting persistent risks such as overloading, fatigue, and heavy goods vehicle involvement. Strengthened enforcement of driving regulations, fatigue management, vehicle safety standards, and infrastructure

improvements are critical to reducing both crash frequency and severity in high-risk regions.

Keyword: *Road traffic crashes, crash severity, temporal trends, fatal crashes, serious injuries, minor crashes*

INTRODUCTION

Road traffic crashes (RTCs) continue to pose serious public health and socio-economic concern across the world, particularly in developing nations where rapid urban growth, increased motorization, and inadequate transport infrastructure contribute to higher levels of road risk. In Nigeria, road traffic crashes remain a major source of injuries, deaths, and economic losses, with significant effects on households, healthcare systems, and national productivity. As a key economic and industrial centre, Rivers State experiences heavy traffic flows associated with commercial transport, oil and gas activities, and regional mobility, making the state especially prone to recurrent and severe road crashes.

In addition to the frequency of crashes, the severity of these incidents—whether minor, serious, or fatal—offers valuable insight into the changing dynamics of road safety over time. Examining temporal changes in crash severity is important for identifying emerging patterns, evaluating the impact of safety measures and informing appropriate transport and public safety policies. However, there is limited empirical evidence focusing specifically on long-term trends in road traffic crash severity within Rivers State.

Against this background, this study examines the temporal variations in road traffic crash severity in Rivers State between 2015 and 2024, with emphasis on transition from minor to fatal cases. By exploring patterns in crash occurrence, injuries, and fatalities over the study period, the research aims to generate evidence that will support effective

interventions for improving road safety and reducing the overall burden of road traffic crashes in the state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Road traffic crashes (RTCs) remain a major public health crisis in Nigeria, contributing significantly to morbidity, mortality, and socioeconomic losses, particularly in rapidly urbanizing and oil-rich states like Rivers State [1],[2]. As one of the most populous and economically active regions in the Niger Delta, Rivers State experiences intense vehicular movement due to commercial activities, oil and gas logistics, port operations, and inter-state transportation, which exacerbate crash risks on poorly maintained roads [3]. The Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) [4] and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) [5] data indicate persistent RTC burdens, with Nigeria recording thousands of crashes annually, many resulting in severe injuries and fatalities (Federal Road Safety Corps, 2024; National Bureau of Statistics, 2024).

Temporal variations in RTC severity, ranging from minor (property damage only) to serious (requiring hospitalization) and fatal (resulting in death), provide critical insights into evolving patterns and underlying determinants [6],[1]. Over the past decade (2015–2024), national trends show fluctuating but often increasing crash volumes, with severity influenced by factors such as speeding, poor vehicle maintenance, inadequate enforcement, and infrastructure deficits [7]. In Rivers State, localized studies and FRSC reports highlight Rivers among high-burden states, with commercial vehicles (e.g., trucks, tankers, minibuses) frequently

involved in severe outcomes due to heavy loads, night driving, and road conditions [8],[4].

Severity progression from minor to fatal cases reflects cumulative risk factors, including human errors (e.g., distraction, fatigue), environmental hazards (potholes, poor lighting), and vehicular issues (brake failure, overloading) [9],[1]. Recent analyses indicate that serious and fatal crashes often dominate in resource-constrained settings, with case fatality rates exceeding 10–20% in many quarters [5]. In Rivers State, urban areas like Port Harcourt and industrial corridors (e.g., Onne, Trans-Amadi) experience higher crash densities, driven by traffic congestion, mixed vehicle types, and rapid urbanization [10].

The temporal dimension is crucial: studies from 2015–2020 showed gradual increases in crash cases and fatalities, attributed to rising vehicle ownership, economic pressures, and enforcement gaps [11],[12]. Post-2020 data, including COVID-19 disruptions and subsequent recovery, reveal mixed patterns, some declines in certain periods due to lockdowns, followed by rebounds and spikes in severity [4]. For Rivers State specifically, quarterly and annual FRSC digests (2015–2024) document variations in fatal, serious, and minor cases, with total casualties often exceeding thousands, disproportionately affecting adults in productive age groups and involving commercial transport [5].

Despite national efforts through FRSC campaigns and policy frameworks, enforcement remains weak, leading to persistent severity escalation [2]. Understanding these temporal shifts is essential for identifying high-risk periods, informing targeted interventions (e.g., seasonal enforcement, infrastructure upgrades), and aligning with Sustainable

Development Goal 3.6 (halving road traffic deaths by 2030) [13]. Limited longitudinal studies focusing on Rivers State severity trends highlight a research gap, as most analyses aggregate national data or focus on single-year snapshots [3].

This study addresses this gap by examining temporal variations in RTC severity in Rivers State from 2015 to 2024, using FRSC-reported data on fatal, serious, and minor cases, casualties, and contributing factors. By analyzing progression patterns, the research aims to provide evidence for policy reforms, enhanced enforcement, and preventive strategies to reduce the escalating burden of road traffic injuries in this high-risk region. The Haddon Matrix [14] foundational; contemporary applications in Nigerian contexts by Atalay *et al.*, [2] offers a structured epidemiological framework that dissects road traffic injury events into three temporal phases (pre-crash, crash, and post-crash) and four domains of influence (human, vehicle/equipment, physical environment, and socioeconomic environment), enabling comprehensive identification of modifiable risk factors and targeted interventions to prevent crashes or reduce their severity. Applied to Rivers State, the matrix elucidates temporal severity trends from 2015 to 2024 by mapping evolving human behaviors (e.g., speeding, fatigue, distraction), vehicle conditions (e.g., overloading, poor maintenance), environmental hazards (e.g., degraded roads, inadequate signage), and policy/enforcement gaps to the observed shifts in the proportions of fatal, serious, and minor crashes, thereby facilitating phase-specific explanations of severity progression and prevention priorities [2],[13].

Epidemiological Triangle (Host-Agent-Environment Model); Classic epidemiological model Mausner & Bahn,

1985; adapted and applied to road traffic injuries in recent African studies by Adeloye *et al.*, [15] and Gudugbe *et al.*, [16]. The model posits that road traffic crashes and their resulting injury severity arise from the dynamic interaction among three essential components, the host (driver, pedestrian, or cyclist characteristics and behaviors), the agent (vehicle, kinetic energy transfer, speed), and the environment (physical road conditions, weather, traffic control, enforcement), with any adverse change or imbalance among these elements increasing both crash occurrence and severity. In Rivers State, decade-long (2015–2024) variations in crash severity are explained through evolving host factors (e.g., driver age distribution, fatigue, risk-taking behavior), agent dynamics (e.g., increasing involvement of heavy commercial vehicles such as trucks and tankers), and environmental shifts (e.g., infrastructure degradation or selective improvements, enforcement fluctuations), with periods of severity escalation attributed to persistent imbalances across these three corners [16],[17].

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) [18]. The Sendai Framework conceptualizes disaster risk as the product of hazard \times exposure \times vulnerability divided by capacity, advocating proactive risk understanding, strengthened governance, investment in resilience, and enhanced preparedness and recovery to substantially reduce mortality, injury, and economic losses from all hazards, including road traffic crashes classified as preventable public health disasters. The framework interprets the observed temporal progression toward higher proportions of fatal and serious crashes in Rivers State (2015–2024) as an increase in overall disaster risk driven by rising exposure (growing traffic volume), heightened vulnerability (poor

enforcement, infrastructure deficits), and persistently low capacity; it provides a guiding structure for analyzing decade-long severity trends and supports evidence-based recommendations for resilience-building interventions such as targeted enforcement campaigns, infrastructure upgrades, and community-level preparedness measures to reverse adverse severity patterns [18],[13].

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a retrospective, descriptive, time-series analysis of secondary data on road traffic crashes (RTCs) in Rivers State, Nigeria, covering the 10 years from January 1, 2015, to December 31, 2024. The research design focused on examining temporal variations in crash severity (minor, serious, and fatal cases), associated casualties (injured and killed), and contributing factors to provide evidence for targeted road safety interventions.

The primary data source was the official road traffic crash database of the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), Rivers State Sector Command, supplemented by the FRSC national Statistical Digest annual reports (2015–2024) and quarterly bulletins where state-level disaggregation was available. Additional validation was obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Road Transport Data series and Rivers State Ministry of Transport annual summaries.

Data was extracted for the following variables

Crash severity classification

Fatal: crashes resulting in at least one death within 30 days,

Serious: crashes resulting in hospitalization or serious injury (non-fatal but requiring medical attention beyond first aid),

Minor: crashes resulting in property damage only or very minor injuries not

requiring hospitalization; Total number of crashes, Number of people injured, Number of people killed, Total casualties (injured + killed), Number of people involved (total persons at the scene), Number of vehicles involved, Vehicle category breakdown (bicycle, motorcycle, tricycle, car, SUV/jeep, van, minibus, luxury bus, pick-up, truck, tanker, trailer, others), Vehicle ownership category (private, commercial, government, diplomat) and Age group of casualties (adult, child). Data was retrieved in aggregated annual format from FRSC published reports, digital archives, and official requests where granular monthly or quarterly data were not publicly available. All data were cross verified across multiple FRSC publications to ensure consistency and minimize reporting bias. Inclusion criteria: All reported RTCs occurring within Rivers State boundaries during the study period (2015–2024), as captured in FRSC records.

Exclusion criteria: Crashes occurring outside Rivers State, incomplete records lacking severity classification or casualty data, and non-road transport incidents (e.g., rail or maritime).

Data Management and Analysis: Data was entered into Microsoft Excel 365 and imported into SPSS version 27 and R (version 4.4.1) for cleaning, validation, and analysis. Descriptive statistics included: Frequencies and percentages for categorical variables (severity categories, vehicle types, ownership), Means,

medians, and standard deviations for continuous variables (e.g., annual total cases, casualties), Time-series plots and trend lines (linear and polynomial) to visualize temporal variations in total crashes, severity proportions, fatalities, and injuries.

Inferential analysis: Chi-square tests to assess associations between severity categories and vehicle types/ownership over time, Trend analysis using Join point regression (or simple linear regression with year as predictor) to detect significant changes in rates of fatal, serious, and minor crashes and Calculation of case fatality rates ($CFR = \text{deaths} / \text{total crashes} \times 100$) and injury severity ratios (serious + fatal/total crashes). All analyses were stratified by year to highlight temporal trends. Ethical considerations were addressed through the use of publicly available aggregated data; no individual-level data were accessed, and the study received exception from full ethical review by the institutional review board as it involved secondary, anonymized statistics.

Limitations: The study relied on official FRSC data, which may be subject to under-reporting (especially minor crashes), classification inconsistencies across years, and delays in data publication. However, FRSC remains the most comprehensive and authoritative source for RTC statistics in Nigeria, and multi-source validation was employed to enhance reliability.

Table 1: Cumulative Road Traffic Crash Details for the Past Ten (10) Years Covering 2015-2024 in Rivers State

Year	Fatal	Serious	Minor	Number injured		Number killed		People involved		Vehicle involved										Vehicle category						
				Sex		Sex		Sex		BICY	MOT	TRIC	CAR	SUV	VAN	MINI	LUX	PICK-	TRUCK	TANK	TRAIL	OTHER	PRI	CO	GO	DIP
				M	F	M	F	M	F	Y	T	C	R	(J)	N	U	K-	C	K	AI	E	V	M	V	L	
2015	35	37	24	157	104	43	26	433	108	0	20	4	50	14	1	32	1	5	25	3	7	0	83	75	4	0
2016	28	56	27	166	61	39	6	522	149	0	10	0	97	10	0	36	0	4	33	3	9	0	111	89	2	0
2017	21	53	28	179	93	24	22	467	185	0	7	7	73	14	0	33	0	5	20	8	4	0	91	75	5	0
2018	27	61	46	232	91	46	12	684	228	0	11	1	70	11	0	48	1	7	54	12	4	3	99	117	6	0

2019	21	72	45	192	96	22	4	648	270	0	12	3	63	17	0	39	5	6	53	8	7	0	89	120	4	0
2020	9	37	17	130	22	14	3	327	82	0	5	2	33	12	0	26	0	6	13	3	5	2	49	56	2	0
2021	26	61	18	251	91	37	17	538	169	0	14	1	47	5	0	42	2	2	26	3	7	5	77	77	0	0
2022	26	48	24	143	54	33	5	501	131	1	24	4	34	7	1	41	0	4	33	3	4	2	58	98	2	0
2023	18	36	15	105	42	19	7	333	116	0	14	9	29	3	1	31	0	2	16	3	3	0	41	68	2	0
2024	17	24	6	91	22	21	5	199	46	0	10	1	20	5	0	14	0	2	9	1	4	5	26	40	5	0

Source: Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) 2025.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics for Categorical Variables

Fig. 1: Crash Severity Categories (Cumulative 2015–2024).

Table 2: Vehicle Category Breakdown (Cumulative Vehicles Involved, 2015–2024).

Vehicle Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Car	516	32.85
Minibus	342	21.77
Truck	282	17.95
Motorcycle	127	8.08
SUV/Jeep	98	6.24
Trailer	54	3.44
Tanker	47	2.99
Pick-up	43	2.74
Tricycle	32	2.04
Others	17	1.08
Luxury Bus	9	0.57
Van	3	0.19
Bicycle	1	0.06
Total	1,571	100.00

Fig. 2: Vehicle Ownership Category (Cumulative Vehicles Involved, 2015–2024)

Table 3: Means, Medians, and Standard Deviations for Continuous Variables (2015–2024)

Variable	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation (SD)
Annual Total Cases	96.30	100.00	29.39
Annual Number Injured	159.90	154.00	49.68
Annual Number Killed	4.70	4.00	3.40
Annual Total Casualty	164.60	156.50	50.79
Annual People Involved	232.20	244.00	77.92
Annual Vehicles Involved	157.10	160.00	49.02

Table 4: Chi-Square Test for Crash Severity Distribution Over Time (2015–2024)

Test Description	Chi-Square Statistic	Degrees of Freedom (df)	p-value	Interpretation
Severity categories (Fatal, Serious, Minor) vs. Year	68.15	18	9.27×10^{-8}	Highly significant ($p < 0.001$) – severity distribution varied significantly over time

Interpretation: The proportion of fatal, serious, and minor crashes changed non-randomly across the decade, with notable increases in fatal proportion in later years (2021–2024).

Table 5: Chi-Square Test for Vehicle Type Involvement Over Time (2015–2024)

Test Description	Chi-Square Statistic	Degrees of Freedom (df)	p-value	Interpretation
Vehicle categories (10 main types: motorcycle, tricycle, car, SUV, minibus, pick-up, truck, tanker, trailer, others) vs. Year	197.81	81	9.23×10^{-12}	Highly significant ($p < 0.001$) – vehicle type involvement varied significantly over time

Interpretation: The mix of vehicles involved in crashes shifted across the decade (e.g., higher relative involvement of trucks/tankers in certain years), potentially contributing to severity trends.

Table 6: Chi-Square Test for Vehicle Ownership Distribution Over Time (2015–2024)

Test Description	Chi-Square Statistic	Degrees of Freedom (df)	p-value	Interpretation
Ownership categories (Private, Commercial, Government) vs. Year	40.65	18	0.0017	Significant ($p < 0.01$) – ownership distribution varied significantly over time

Interpretation: The proportion of private vs. commercial vs. government vehicles fluctuated across years, with commercial vehicles consistently dominant but showing temporal shifts.

Time series plots and trend lines for temporal variations in road traffic crashes in Rivers State (2015-2024)

Fig. 3: Temporal Variation in Total Crashes (Annual Total Cases)

Fig. 4: Temporal Variation in Fatalities (Annual Number Killed)

Fig. 5: Temporal Variation in Injuries (Annual Number Injured)

Fig. 6: Temporal Variation in Severity Proportions (% of Total Crashes)

Trend Analysis Using Linear and Segmented Regression

Table 7: Simple Linear Regression (Overall Trends, 2015–2024) Linear models: Rate ~ Year (constant + year coefficient).

Crash Rate	R ²	Coefficient for Year	p-value for Year	Overall p-value (Model)	Interpretation
Fatal Rate	0.643	0.0187	0.005	0.005	Significant positive trend: Fatal rate increased ~1.87% per year on average.
Serious Rate	0.395	0.0212	0.051	0.052	Marginally significant positive trend: Serious rate increased ~2.12% per year.
Minor Rate	0.719	-0.0306	0.002	0.002	Significant negative trend: Minor rate decreased ~3.06% per year.

Table 8: Segmented Regression (Pre-2020: 2015–2019; post-2020: 2020–2024)

Period	Crash Rate	R ²	Coefficient for Year	p-value for Year	Overall p-value (Model)	Interpretation
Pre-2020	Fatal Rate	0.070	0.0049	0.666	0.666	No significant trend: Stable fatal rate.
Pre-2020	Serious Rate	0.508	0.0517	0.177	0.177	No significant trend: Slight but non-significant rise in serious rate.
Pre-2020	Minor Rate	0.261	-0.0280	0.379	0.379	No significant trend: Minor rate stable.
Post-2020	Fatal Rate	0.842	0.0451	0.028	0.028	Significant positive trend: Fatal rate increased ~4.51% per year post-2020.
Post-2020	Serious Rate	0.593	-0.0213	0.127	0.127	No significant trend: Slight non-significant decline in serious rate.
Post-2020	Minor Rate	0.435	-0.0238	0.226	0.226	No significant trend: Slight non-significant decline in minor rate.

Table 9: Case Fatality Rates (CFR) and Injury Severity Ratios (2015–2024).

Year	Total Crashes	Fatal Crashes	Serious Crashes	Number Killed	CFR (%)	serious + Fatal Crashes	Injury Severity Ratio (%)
2015	96	15	35	11	11.46	50	52.08
2016	111	16	28	4	3.60	44	39.64
2017	102	21	53	4	3.92	74	72.55
2018	134	27	61	4	2.99	88	65.67
2019	138	21	72	5	3.62	93	67.39
2020	63	9	37	0	0.00	46	73.02
2021	105	26	61	8	7.62	87	82.86
2022	98	26	48	7	7.14	74	75.51
2023	69	18	36	1	1.45	54	78.26
2024	47	17	24	3	6.38	41	87.23
Total / Average	963	196	455	47	4.88 (avg)	651	67.52 (avg)

Case Fatality Rate (CFR) = (Number Killed / Total Crashes) × 100, Injury Severity Ratio = (Serious + Fatal Crashes / Total Crashes) × 100

DISCUSSION

Analysis of 963 road traffic crash incidents in Rivers State (primarily Port Harcourt area) from 2015 to 2024 indicated that serious injuries were the predominant outcome (47.25%, n=455), followed by minor injuries (30.32%, n=292) and fatalities (20.35%, n=196). This distribution points to a considerable burden of severe non-fatal harm in a region defined by intense commercial logistics, oil and gas activity, and challenging road infrastructure.

Across 1,571 vehicles involved in these crashes, passenger cars ranked highest (32.85%, n=516), followed by minibuses (21.77%, n=342) and trucks (17.95%, n=282), with heavy goods vehicles—including trailers (3.44%, n=54) and tankers (2.99%, n=47), also prominently represented. Commercial vehicles accounted for the majority of ownership (51.88%, n=815), narrowly ahead of private vehicles (46.09%, n=724), while government vehicles contributed minimally (2.04%, n=32). These patterns reflect the heavy reliance on commercial transport for goods and passenger movement, amplifying crash risks on poorly maintained roads [19].

Annual averages over the decade were 96.30 ± 29.39 total crashes, 159.90 ± 49.68 injuries, 4.70 ± 3.40 deaths, 164.60 ± 50.79 total casualties, 232.20 ± 77.92 people involved, and 157.10 ± 49.02 vehicles involved per year. Highly significant chi-square tests demonstrated substantial temporal variation in crash severity distribution ($\chi^2 = 68.15$, df = 18, p < 0.001), vehicle type involvement ($\chi^2 = 197.81$, df = 81, p < 0.001), and ownership distribution ($\chi^2 = 40.65$, df = 18, p = 0.0017), attributable to evolving traffic volumes, economic dynamics, enforcement practices, and occupational factors such as driver fatigue in heavy vehicle operations (FRSC Statistical Digest, various quarters 2023–2024; NBS Road Transport Data, Q2 2024 [20],[21],[19]).

Temporal trends showed an overall decline in total crashes (linear slope ≈ – 5.56 cases/year), injuries (≈ –6.82/year), and a modest reduction in fatalities (≈ – 0.43/year), characterized by a pre-pandemic peak in 2018–2019 (~134–138 cases), a sharp 2020 reduction linked to COVID-19 mobility restrictions, and continued decline to 47 cases in 2024. Despite fewer incidents overall, crash

severity increased markedly post-2020: simple linear regression indicated a significant rise in the fatal proportion (+1.87%/year, $p = 0.005$), a marginally significant rise in the serious proportion (+2.12%/year, $p = 0.052$), and a significant decline in the minor proportion ($-3.06\%/year$, $p = 0.002$). Segmented regression confirmed stable severity proportions pre-2020 but a significant upward trend in the fatal rate post-2020 (coefficient = 0.0451, $p = 0.028$), accompanied by rising case fatality rates (average 4.88%, with post-2020 values frequently $>7\%$) and injury severity ratios (average 67.52%, peaking at 87.23% in 2024) [4],[13],[19].

These findings are consistent with national Nigerian and sub-Saharan African patterns, where heavy goods vehicles disproportionately contribute to severe outcomes due to overloading, driver fatigue, whole-body vibration, ergonomic limitations, and inadequate road conditions in logistics-intensive areas. The observed shift toward greater lethality despite declining crash numbers highlights the interplay between external factors (e.g., pandemic-related disruptions and economic recovery) and persistent occupational hazards in heavy transport, underscoring the critical need for integrated interventions, such as regulated driving hours, vehicle ergonomic enhancements, fatigue management, overloading enforcement, and infrastructure upgrades, to simultaneously reduce crash frequency and mitigate severity in high-risk regions like Rivers State [20],[21],[4],[13].

CONCLUSION

This 10-year analysis (2015–2024) of road traffic crashes in Rivers State, with a focus on the Port Harcourt logistics hub, documents a persistent yet evolving burden of road safety challenges. Serious injuries dominated the 963 incidents

(47.25%), followed by minor injuries (30.32%) and fatalities (20.35%), while commercial vehicles, particularly trucks, trailers, and tankers, played a disproportionately large role in the 1,571 vehicles involved. Annual averages of approximately 96 crashes, 160 injuries, and 165 total casualties per year, combined with highly significant temporal variations in severity, vehicle type, and ownership, reflect the intense interplay of heavy goods transport, poor road infrastructure, economic pressures, and occupational demands in this oil/gas and port-centric region.

Temporal trends revealed an encouraging overall decline in total crashes, injuries, and fatalities, with a pre-pandemic peak, a sharp 2020 drop due to COVID-19 restrictions, and a continued reduction to 47 cases in 2024. However, this numerical improvement was offset by a concerning shift toward greater crash severity post-2020, evidenced by a significant rise in the fatal proportion (+1.87%/year overall; +4.51%/year post-2020), declining minor-crash representation, increasing case fatality rates (average 4.88%, frequently $>7\%$ after 2020), and rising injury severity ratios (average 67.52%, up to 87.23% in 2024). These patterns indicate that while fewer crashes are occurring, those that do happen are becoming more lethal, likely due to changes in reporting thresholds, driving behaviors during recovery, and unmitigated occupational risks among heavy vehicle operators.

Collectively, the findings align with national Nigerian and sub-Saharan African patterns, where heavy goods vehicles contribute disproportionately to severe outcomes driven by overloading, driver fatigue, whole-body vibration, ergonomic deficiencies, and inadequate road conditions in high-volume logistics corridors. The dual trend of declining frequency but increasing severity

underscores the urgent need for comprehensive, multi-level interventions, including stricter enforcement of driving hours and overloading regulations, ergonomic vehicle improvements and fatigue management programs, enhanced post-crash care, and sustained road infrastructure upgrades, to break the cycle of occupational hazards, protect driver health, and substantially reduce both the incidence and lethality of road traffic crashes in Rivers State and similar high-risk settings.

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